

Designing and Developing Supplementary Reading Comprehension Material in English Integrating the Local Content of Tinambac Camarines Sur for Brigada Pagbasa Students

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Abstract:- This paper designed and developed supplementary reading comprehension material in English which integrate the local content of Tinambac, Camarines Sur for Brigada Pagbasa Students. It employed Research and Development method which included the analysis of the reading comprehension level of students, collection of local content in Tinambac, development of the local content supplementary material, and content validation of the material. Results shared that no local literatures were used as content in the brigada pagbasa material existing in the municipality. Local content in Tinambac were identified through key informants and cultural mapping tool. These were integrated into the development of supplementary reading material. The organization of the content was guided by ADDIE Model of Instructional Design and subjected to content validation and acceptability. The validation of the material was determined through Cronbach alpha while 4-point Likert scale was used to determine the content validity and acceptability of the supplementary reading material. The evaluation by experts for acceptability yielded 3.87 considered as highly acceptable in all areas. Regression Analysis was used to determine how the developed supplementary reading material contributed significantly to the reading comprehension of the students. Results showed that the positive coefficient implies that an increase in the result of the supplementary reading material will result to higher level of reading comprehension. The study recommended the conduct of the study to other districts. Also, language teachers are encouraged to localize learning materials integrating the local content of different municipalities in the province.

Keywords:- Local Content Supplementary Reading Materials, Local Content, Reading Comprehension.

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has paved the way for the implementation of Modular Distance Learning as an urgent response to ensure continuity of education here in the country. Our country as of this moment is in the process of adapting to the new normal form of education and continuous innovations

of educators and the active involvement of other stakeholders are the driving force for its success (Dangle & Sumaoang, 2020). It becomes the duty of the teacher to keep an eye on the students' development. The students can contact the teacher via phone, text message, instant messaging, email, or another method. When feasible, the teachers will visit the students who require help or remediation. However, not all students have the capacity to learn in the new setup of the teaching-learning process.

Many issues related to teaching and learning particularly in literacy and numeracy have been emerging. This was disclosed in an article published in The Philippine Daily Inquirer (2014) that among the 38 countries in Southeast Asia, the Philippines ranked 36th in English

Language Proficiency. This can be seen in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). Results revealed that almost 80% of the students did not meet the minimum level of proficiency in reading and even dropped down because of the pandemic that led to “learning loss” as coined by UNICEF (Dangle & Sumaoang, 2020; Labadista, 2021).

The gaps in learners' reading comprehension are found to be one of the causes leading to low achievement in English, Math, and Science. Ordinario (2013), presented DepEd data showing that the average NAT (National Achievement Test) scores of public secondary school students for the SY 2011-2012 were significantly lower at 48.90%. Imam, Mastura, and Jamil (2013), stated that the overall students' performance in reading comprehension and Science was indexed at a low mastery level in Cotabato public secondary schools. In the school-based context, the School's Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Group Screening Test (GST) resulted in one of the schools in Tinambac which was conducted by experts in the field. It can be noted from the result that only 44% of the students in the **Brigada Pagbasa** program demonstrated reading comprehension. In particular, 36% exhibited strength in **literal comprehension**, while 27% showed weaknesses at the **inferential level**. In addition, only 32% among the students exhibited proficiency in critical reading comprehension.

In response to the reading difficulties deemed both from the international and local perspectives, reading programs and interventions have been made. To enhance the comprehension skills of learners, the “Drop Everything and Read” (DEAR) issued under DepEd Memorandum No. 244, series 2011 was implemented to encourage students to do independent silent reading during their extended period. It also gives students time to read their choices of materials based on their interests, etc. Likewise, the Department of Education launched the Brigada Pagbasa in response to the call to intensify the advocacy for reading. This intends to cater to learners who are below 18 years old, focusing on non-readers and struggling readers from both formal and non-formal education systems nationwide. The Department also strengthens reading programs as part of delivering quality education to Filipino learners as in line—with the government’s Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), a global target for the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Quality Education.

However, in action research conducted by Esposa (2019), he stated that “there are no specific plans and remediation activities implemented in English subjects intended to cater to these struggling readers’ needs.” Thus, from the merits of the interventions stated above in responding to reading difficulties, the researcher saw hope and deemed it necessary to develop another learning material that may address issues on reading comprehension to help resolve reading challenges.

Czerkowski, B., & Berti, M. (2020) stated that, with the advent of 21st-century learning, issues arise, and teachers are now required to develop instructional materials that will aid the needs of the learners. Thus, the flexibility of the curriculum must be seen in the academe through integrating local culture and traditions. Regmi (2017) states that integrating texts with the local culture will lessen the unfamiliarity and help students to read better. With this, the Division of Camarines Sur encouraged all teachers to localize all learning materials using local content. This underscored the development of reading comprehension material in English integrating the local content of Tinambac, Camarines Sur to address the pervading issues stated in this paper. Specifically, it a) determine the level of reading comprehension of the brigada pagbasa students in terms of: Literal; Inferential; and Critical, b) develop supplementary reading comprehension material in English integrating the local content of Tinambac, Camarines Sur, c) determine the level of acceptability of the developed supplementary reading comprehension material in English, d) determine the level of reading comprehension of the brigada pagbasa students using the developed supplementary reading comprehension material and, e) determine how the supplementary reading comprehension material in English contributes significantly to the reading comprehension skills of the brigada pagbasa students.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study employed Research and Development (R&D) design. Purposive sampling was used to identify the key informants of this study. The classification of local content was based on the cultural mapping tool adapted from NCCA. This covered the historical description of local intangible and tangible culture such as legend, history, religious tales, etc. The old folks ranging from 60 and up who can still speak and write, municipal and tourism officers, and informants who have knowledge and ideas on the local culture of Tinambac served as key informants and source of data.

The development of the supplementary reading material was done through: a) the results of the Brigada Pagbasa Phil-IRI Group Screening Test were determined for the analysis. This was considered a gap to be filled in crafting supplementary local content-based reading material. The developed local content-based supplementary reading material was the same type as the existing reading comprehension materials used by the brigada pagbasa students wherein the reading comprehension levels were presented in the questions; b) craft literature using the collected local content of Tinambac appropriate on the gaps. The researcher crafts literature to be validated by Schools Division of Camarines Sur English teachers, writers and editors, and school heads; c) Develop local content-based supplementary reading material using the literature crafted adopting the ADDIE Model of Instructional Design and the Phil-IRI Group Screening Test format with some modifications.

The assessment of content validity and acceptability of supplementary local content-based reading material focused on the guide questions and supplementary reading activities to strengthen the reading comprehension of the material’s users. While acceptability focused on the coherence and clarity of thought, language, content, format, book layout and design, and typographical organization. The survey questionnaire was utilized by the thirty (30) respondents comprised of 2 Division Writers/Validators, 5 ICT experts, 13 language teachers, 5 school head teachers, and 5 school master teachers whose expertise is related to instructional material development to determine the level of acceptability of the local content-based reading material. The regression analysis was used to see the significant contribution of the developed supplementary reading material to the comprehension skills of the students. The recommendations and suggestions were integrated to the revision of the content of the supplementary reading comprehension material using local content.

III. RESULTS

A. Level of the Reading Comprehension of the Brigada Pagbasa Students

Table 3 shows the level of the Reading Comprehension of the Brigada Pagbasa students before they were exposed to the Developed Supplementary Reading Comprehension Material in terms of literal, inferential, and critical.

In literal, based on the data, the indicator falling under Needs Improvement (NI) were: Literal with mean: 2.154, SD: 0.53, PL: 35.89; Inferential with mean: 2.450, SD: 0.76, PL: 27.22; and Critical with mean: 1.607, SD: 0.41, PL: 32.14. Additionally, based on the result, the over-all results implied that the over-all mean was 6.211 with a performance level of 31.05 which falls under the Needs Improvement. These results were used as baseline data to design and develop supplementary reading comprehension material in English integrating the LocalContent of Tinambac, Camarines Sur for

Brigada Pagbasa Recipients and to determine the impact of the developed supplementary reading comprehension material to the comprehension skills of the brigada pagbasa students.

The results of the test after the students were exposed to the Supplementary Reading Comprehension Material were compared to the findings of the learners’ reading comprehension profile.

Table 1: Level of the Reading Comprehension of the Brigada Pagbasa Students Using the Brigada Pagbasa Material

Reading Comprehension Level	No. of Items	Mean	SD	PL	Int	Rank
1. Literal	6	2.154	0.53	35.89	NI	1
2. Inferential	9	2.450	0.76	27.22	NI	3
3. Critical	5	1.607	0.41	32.14	NI	2
Average	20	2.073	0.57	31.75	NI	

Legend: Performance Level (PL)

90 and above	-	Outstanding (O)	SD - Standard Deviation
80-89	-	Very Satisfactory (VS)	Int - Interpretation
74-79	-	Satisfactory (S)	PL - Performance Level
66-73	-	Nearing Mastery (NM)	
65 below	-	Needs Improvement (NI)	

B. Design of the Supplementary Reading Comprehension Material in English Integrating the Local-Content of Tinambac Camarines Sur for Brigada Pagbasa Students

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher developed supplementary reading comprehension material that would overcome the reading difficulty. It aims to help learners independently and develop an interest in reading. As a supplementary reading tool, it would reinforce further the reading comprehension skills to achieve independent reading. The supplementary reading material will provide appropriate and abundant practice in reading comprehension. It aims to lead the child on the way to literacy and proficiency.

Table 2 shows different stories integrating the local content of Tinambac and a variety of activities. This shows the stories and sample learning outcomes of the Developed Supplementary Reading Comprehension Material in English under Fiction Stories Integrating Local Content of Tinambac, Camarines Sur. The first part of the reading material is given to test the reading comprehension of the students. The following activities were given to ensure that they understand what they have read. After the provision of all necessary information, the tool itself will successfully provide the following: a) Reading Selections; and b) Variety of Activities.

Table 2: Stories Created out of the Local Collected in Tinambac, Camarines Sur

<i>Title of the Stories</i>	<i>Summary of the Stories</i>	<i>Reading Learning Outcomes</i>
<p><i>Tinambac- Itself</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>Oral history claims that himoragat was the ancient name of Tinambac which passed to oblivion when it was replaced by the present name of Tinambac. Spanish records however seemed to tell a different story. Himoragat and Tinambac were two distinct geographic territories which remained until about the early decades of the 19th century when the name himoragat gradually passed out of existence. The origin of these names remains virtually obscure.</p> <p>Folk stories followed the typical pattern of explanation of the emergence of place names. Popular belief claims that the name arose out of some confusion in the course of a chance encounter between a group of Spanish exploring parties and the natives. Arriving at the seashore, the Spaniards who saw them inquired about the name of the place. But unable to understand the castilian language, the natives who thought that the Spaniards were asking for their catch told them that this was a pile of wild boar and deer. "Tambak na Osa" they told the foreigners as they pointed to the heap of these animals. Hearing the sound Tambac, the Spaniards began calling the place Tambac. A more reasoned guess could be drawn from the native lexicon of the 16th-century context of the word tambac.</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Identify words used from readings to complete sentences. Determine the meaning of the underlined words to understand the text. Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text. Respond to the reading in a variety of written forms.
<p><i>The Oldest Person in Tierra Nevada</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>Wenceslao Romeo Luna is the oldest person in Tierra Nevada, he became a barangay captain twice before and served for 15 years. He now lives with his family in Quewaye, where only a few people live. For over 98 years, he's been watching everything he loves, vanishing from his life and not being able to do something about it like he's paralyzed. Slowly losing people he loves. Slowly giving up on his dreams. Slowly abandoning his hobbies. Slowly killing parts of me. And it would be no wonder if in the end, all he's left with is a dead soul. Everyone said that this was a part of growing up. But no one taught him how to cope with the pain that comes with the loss when he gets older with time and everything seems surreal.</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text. Respond to the reading in a variety of written forms.
<p><i>The Healer</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>In the barangay of Sta. Cruz, there is a sitio called Magrimpong. Magrimpong is where Manuel is living, he is a faith healer and a bladesmith. Manuel performs a ritual every second Friday of the month. Through the help of his mind and blade and a little oration, Manuel can heal not only the sick but also those who are being possessed without asking for anything in return, but he can only heal ten people because of the rules he follows. At an early age, he started performing the ritual because his parents had passed it on to him. Since then, Manuel has continued treating people willingly.</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the correct spelling of the words Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text. Respond to the reading in a variety of written forms. Use given words to form sentences.
<p><i>Chapel of the Holy Sepulcher</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>Once there were five families in the barangay of Sta. Cruz, who maintains the tradition of offering mass to Hinulid. The Mendez, Abiog, Brugada, Borja, and Sarmiento Family. They are the devoted caretakers of the saint and help each other to cover all the maintenance and needs of every mass. By the time, the mass for Hinulid is only being held at one of the houses of the five families. Because of the growing number of devotees, they needed more space to accommodate all the attendees and that is when the Abiog Family decided to build a chapel for all the devotees to gather. After they opened it to the public, a priest set a schedule for the mass every 2nd Friday of the month. They also gather and unite every 15th of February to celebrate the anniversary of the chapel. Later on, the five families donated the chapel to the parish of St. Paschal Baylon and lived a happy and religious life.</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Determine the meaning of words Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text. Point out words used from readings.
<p><i>Barangay Tierra Nevada History</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>Tierra Nevada is one of the biggest barangays in the municipality of Tinambac, situated near the foot of Mount Isarog. The barrio was formerly known as Toril or Tinorilan due to the presence of fenced and enclosed areas for animals. A foreigner once lived there and built a cattle ranch upon knowing that people were honest. It was discovered by a Spaniard who started farming crops, the name of the barrio was related to the cool breeze and good soil. The foremost inhabitants came from Goa, Nabua, Lagonoy, and Iriga. These places took an active part in the revolution against the superiority of the Spanish. Tierra Nevada was also the place who was not spared by the Japanese occupation and many people died</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text. Respond to the reading in a variety of written forms. Use words to form sentences

<p><i>Pascual to San Paschal Baylon</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>Once upon a time, there was a boy named Pascual. He was born at Toree Hermosa, in the Kingdom of Aragon on 2 May 1540. His parents, Martin Baylon and Elizabeth or Isabel Jubera, were poor but virtuous peasants.</p> <p>As a young boy, Pascual already showed conspicuous sins of his unusual devotion towards the Holy Eucharist. It was the devotion which formed the distinctive mark of his saintly character. From his seventh until his twenty-fourth year, he led the lowly life of a shepherd. Shortly thereafter, he entered the religious life and was admitted as a lay brother among the Franciscans of the Alcantarine Reform.</p> <p>In his cloistered life, Pascual's charity to the poor and the afflicted was remarkable. Although poorly educated, San Pascual wise counsels were sought by people coming from various stations in life. After living a sanctity, Pascual died in Villa Real on May 15, 1592 at the age of 52. In 1618, twenty-four year after his death, Pascual was beatified. But it took him some 72 years before he was finally canonized in 1690. The great story of the saint quickly spread to the various missions' outposts of the Spanish empire particularly to those under the</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate understanding of the text (such as images, comic strip, etc.) Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text. Respond to the reading in a variety of written forms.
<p><i>San Pascual Barangay Hall</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>during that time due to torture and schools were also burned to the ground. Apparently, the barrios were still called by its former name.</p> <p>1980-1990 is the year wherein the First Barangay Hall of San Pascual, Tinambac Camarines Sur was created, people were so happy and celebrated the opening of the hall. This place is located near the Public Cemetery of Tinambac which is why, whenever Soul's Day approached, bad people could not do something because the whole place was secured by barangay personnel. Time went by and in 2013 it was beautified under the administration of the Barangay Captain, Crisanto Abrera. The color of the building is blue and the floor is made of white rile. This place is not hard to find for the name, "Brgy. MULTI-PURPOSE BUILDING" is written on the front of it. Outside the hall, there is a Multi-purpose covered court where young men play basketball. A day-care center, and health care center which is always available to help the citizens of the barangay, and the map of the barangay.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> By the end of reading, students will be able to: Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text. Show a sense of commitment through active involvement in the activity
<p><i>David Amparado Rosales</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>Franciscans. His life became an inspiration among the priests and laymen. His feast is kept on May 17. Now, he is the patron saint of San Paschal Baylon Church.</p> <p>Why are you looking for my grandfather?" I asked. "Ah, yes. We are from Naga City and we have a project to do. Which is making a story out of the Heritage in your place. Here's our approved letter from your barangay captain. We are just here to interview and take some photos of one of the famous people in this place who performs rituals." I nodded as they explained.</p> <p>"David Amporado Rosales is his full name. He is now an 83-year-old man and is serving this place for 68 years. He is one of the oldest people in Sagrada, Tinambac, Camarines Sur that is still performing rituals to heal and help those people who are sick and/or injured just like your friend, and those who are bitten by dangerous animals using herbals. In his service, people's trust was built. This place cannot be emptied even once unless he's not feeling okay. He also creates protection from bad spirits that are done using the Latin Language. His age doesn't bother how he performs. I might say that my grandfather is now a veteran in this field."</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text Show a sense of commitment through active involvement in the activity
<p><i>Why Buenavista?</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>Land of happiness.</p> <p>In the Spanish period, the Moros came to capture the Christians, so a fight broke out in the city. A guy single-handedly faced them. They were defeated by his miracle. His act of facing them singlehandedly like a bull crashing into a battalion was the reason it was named "Brgy. Binangga." The name of the miraculous guy was San Pascual Baylon, who became the patron saint of Tinambac. However, due to lashing forestry and an abundance of trees, it was changed to "Brgy. Binoot" after a short time. In the American period of 1902, a politician visited the place. He was Sr. Francisco Torra. In his travels and sightings of Brgy. Binoot, named it Buenavista because he thought it was beautiful in his eyes and because buenavista means "the land of happiness."</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text Respond to the reading in a variety of written forms.

<p><i>Barangay Filarca, Named after the Mayor</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>Long time ago, barangay filarca doesn't have a name. The place is known for the crystal-clear water that flows alongside the barangay. Although the river is beautiful and pleasing, no one dares to swim or wash their clothes in there because of the wild animals and venomous snakes infesting the area. Year 1918 when Don Cepriano Filarca was elected as the mayor of the municipality of Tinambac. After sitting in the position, he immediately acted and conducted ground clearing operations along the river which made the place a lot safer. To</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Demonstrate understanding of the text by supplying the missing letters to form words. b. Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension.
	<p>honor the efforts of the mayor, the locals decided to name the barangay after the mayor himself, barangay Filarca.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text d. Arrange words chronologically.
<p><i>The DAR Office</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>One of the things to determine whether a place is already old enough is when there are already abandoned buildings. In Zone 2, San Ramon, Tinambac, Camarines Sur is where the old DAR office is located. 65 years have passed and the building was already abandoned. From 1957 until 1980 the office was still in use, but of course, things won't last in this world unless treated better and with so much care. In the year the 2000s, the DAR office was no longer used. The place is being piled with cement by people to reach the top of it because it's on the higher level of the barangay, but safety is no longer guaranteed because even the stairs are slowly giving up. After all, it's already old enough to have cracks and destroyed parts.</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. b. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text c. Respond to the reading in a variety of written forms.
<p><i>Barbecho's Residence: One of the Oldest Houses</i></p> <p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>The amazing thing to tell is when your house has a history from colonization. Why? Because it is a living proof that we can see and study. That the history of colonization is not just a story but the truth. Just like the house of the Barbechos from Zone 1, La Purisima, Tinambac, Camarines Sur. It is located beside the La Purisima Multi-Purpose Hall and in front of the house is a diner, an old diner to be exact. What exactly is the most exciting part of a story? It's history. Barbecho's house is one of the oldest houses in Tinambac. It was estimated living for already 61 years and is not originally theirs but of the late Petra Borromeo, it is only inherited by Dolores Barbecho, wife of Mamerto Barbecho when Petra Borromeo adopted her. The house was said to be the hiding place way back when the Japanese came. The house looks small on the outside but is spacious inside, it can be seen and noticed at night through its lighting.</p>	<p>By the end of reading, students will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. b. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text c. Show a sense of commitment through active involvement in the activity
<p>(Discuss how different contexts enhance the text's meaning and enrich the reader's understanding)</p>	<p>Teneiente Del barrio also known as Cabeza de Barangay and sincerely committed to the public service. After the leadership of Martiano Agsangre, the barangay has celebrated of feast of the Holy Cross as a Patron Saint, only the celebration of Sta. Cruzan during the month of May. Ricardo Vale was the next Teniente Del Barrio, who declared the first celebration of the feast day in honor of patron Saint Holy Cross on May 03, 1950, and it happened every year since then. But during the term of former Barangay Captain Teresita C. Abiog from 1977 - 2002, the traditional celebration of feast day changed to September 13-14 based on how the triumph of the Holy Cross to be resurrection of Christ-His Triumph over death found and revision of the Feast Day was the decision of Cora Paruco Fr. Mario Gaité, the Parish Priest of Saint Paschal Baylon and majority approved by the constituents during the Barangay Assembly of Barangay Sta. Cruz, Tinambac, Camarines Sur. The chapel of the barangay was founded through the effort of the Barangay Pastoral Council, barangay Officials and concerned citizens donated financially.</p> <p>Barangay Sta. Cruz is one of the coastal barangays of San Miguel Bay which experienced the trend of low catch.</p> <p>The barangay has a total land area of 262 hectares. It is considered as one of the largest barangays within the poblacion area. Approximately 80% of the total area is used as residential and the remaining 20% is used in farming and construction of the other landmarks found in barangay.</p> <p>Characterized by fertile low and up-land area along the coastal plains of San Miguel Bay, the economic base of the barangay had been traditionally anchored on two primary industries, namely agriculture and fishing which shall remain up to the present.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Identify words used from readings to complete sentences. b. Determine the meaning of words c. Read and analyze the reading text to support comprehension. d. Respond to the questions to demonstrate understanding of the text

C. The Level of Acceptability of the Developed Reading Material

Table 3 shows the different indicators included for the validation of coherence and clarity of thought of the developed supplementary reading comprehension material in English integrating the local content of Tinambac, Camarines Sur for brigada pagbasa students. It can be observed that in the respondent’s evaluation, all indicators were rated Highly Acceptable. The coherence and clarity of thought of the statements/phrases make sense (3.90); The sentences in the paragraph contribute to one idea (3.93); The thoughts/ideas logically sequenced (3.83); The choice of words/expressions are appropriate (3.83); The language are appropriate for the target learners (3.83); The vocabulary level is adapted to target users’ experience and understanding (3.83); The length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target user (3.87); The sentences and paragraph structures are varied and appropriate to the target user (3.87); The material

provides an activity that will enhance the learner’s understanding of concepts (3.90).

Therefore, the manifestation of the said results implies that the researcher herself conducted a thorough consultation of the coherence and clarity of thought of the developed supplementary reading material during the process of framing and carefully setting the material and that these are indeed necessary to the developed supplementary reading material. Furthermore, the respondent’s evaluation of the acceptability of the coherence and clarity of thought of the developed supplementary reading material resulted in 3.87 interpreted as Highly Acceptable (HA). Therefore, the researcher concluded that the developed supplementary reading material were highly acceptable in its coherence and clarity 68 of thought. It only means that the respondents found this indicator highly acceptable in setting the goals of the learning experience that would transpire with the use of the said material.

Table 3: Acceptability of the Developed Supplementary Reading Comprehension Material in Terms of Coherence and Clarity of Thought

Indicators	Average		
	Wx	Int	Rank
1. The statements/phrases make sense	3.90	HA	2.5
2. The sentences in the paragraph contribute to one idea	3.93	HA	1
3. The thoughts/ideas logically sequenced	3.83	HA	7.5
4. The choice of words/expressions are appropriate	3.83	HA	7.5
5. The language is appropriate for the target learners	3.83	HA	7.5
6. The vocabulary level is adapted to target users’ experience and understanding	3.83	HA	7.5
7. The length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target user	3.87	HA	4.5
8. The sentences and paragraph structures are varied and appropriate to the target user	3.87	HA	4.5
9. The material provides an activity that will enhance the learner’s understanding of concepts	3.90	HA	2.5
Average	3.87	HA	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Highly Acceptable (HA) 2.51 – 3.25 Acceptable (V) 1.00 - 1.75 Highly Rejected (HR) 1.76 - 2.50 Rejected (R)

Table 4 shows that the language/content/format of the developed supplementary reading material in English is highly acceptable. It can be observed from the respondents’ evaluation, that all of the indicators got an average weighted mean of 3.88 which is interpreted as Highly Acceptable (HA). Taking into account the indicators evaluated, the results confirmed that the general contents which the developed material used vocabulary that are within the learner’s level of comprehension (3.90); The developed material structure of sentences are appropriate to the learners (3.87); The words, whether local or foreign, correctly spelled (3.83); The developed material free from grammatical errors (3.93); The length and structure of sentences are appropriate to the learners (3.93); The total number of pages of the material is sufficient to carry out the intended lesson (3.90); The material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the learning area and grade level for which it is intended (3.83); Content is suitable to the target learner’s level of

development, needs, experience (3.87); Content reinforces, enriches, and / or leads to the mastery of the targeted learning competencies intended for the learning area and grade level (3.87); The material develops higher cognitive skills (e.g., critical thinking skills, creativity, learning by doing, problem solving) (3.90). These all are aligned with the objectives of the lesson ensuring their relevance.

The results also imply that it could provide learners the instructional strategies that would be effective for cognitive, psychomotor, and affective learning since the objectives are developed using Bloom’s Taxonomy (Adams, 2015). The results further imply that the language/content/format is suitable to the learner’s ability and needs. Suitability 72 is attained when the contents are student-centered and goal-oriented coupled with relevant activities (Reiser & Dempsey, 2012).

Table 4: Acceptability of the Developed Supplementary Reading Comprehension Materials in Terms of Language/Content/Format

Indicators	Average		Rank
	Wx	Int	
1. The developed material Used vocabulary that is within the learner's level of comprehension	3.90	HA	4
2. The developed material structure of sentences is appropriate for the learners	3.87	HA	7
3. The words, whether local or foreign, are correctly spelled	3.83	HA	9.5
4. The developed material free from grammatical errors	3.93	HA	1.5
5. The length and structure of sentences are appropriate for the learners	3.93	HA	1.5
6. The total number of pages of the material is sufficient to carry out the intended lesson.	3.90	HA	4
7. The material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the learning area and grade level for which it is intended.	3.83	HA	9.5
8. Content is suitable to the target learner's level of development, needs, experience	3.87	HA	7
9. Content reinforces, enriches, and/or leads to the mastery of the targeted learning competencies intended for the learning area and grade level	3.87	HA	7
10. The material develops higher cognitive skills (e.g., critical thinking skills, creativity, learning by doing, problem-solving)	3.90	HA	4
Average	3.88	HA	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Highly Acceptable (HA) 2.51 – 3.25 Acceptable (V) 1.00 - 1.75 Highly Rejected (HR) 1.76 - 2.50 Rejected (R)

The presentation and style of the developed supplementary reading material as shown in Table 5 are highly acceptable. It can be observed from the respondents' evaluation, that all of the indicators got an average weighted mean of 3.84 which is interpreted as Highly Acceptable (HA). The results confirmed that the following indicators which

Unit/chapter/lesson titles & subheads are consistent in style (3.93); Attractive and pleasing to look at (3.77); Simple (i.e., does not distract the attention of the readers) (3.83). Thus, this can be concluded that the layout and design of the developed supplementary reading material passed the standards of the experts.

Table 5: Acceptability of the Developed Supplementary Reading Comprehension Materials in Terms of Book Layout and Design

Indicators	Average				Rank
	Wx	Int	Wx	Int	
1. Unit/chapter/lesson titles & subheads are consistent in style	3.80	HA	3.93	HA	1
2. Attractive and pleasing to look at	3.40	HA	3.77	HA	2.5
3. Simple (i.e., does not distract the attention of the readers)	3.80	HA	3.83	HA	2.5
Average	3.67	HA	3.84	HA	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Highly Acceptable (HA) 2.51 – 3.25 Acceptable (V) 1.00 - 1.75 Highly Rejected (HR) 1.76 - 2.50 Rejected (R)

Table 6 shows the different indicators included for the validation of Typographical Organization of the developed supplementary reading comprehension material in English integrating the local content of Tinambac, Camarines Sur for brigada pagbasa students. It can be observed that in the respondent's evaluation, all indicators were rated Highly Acceptable. Thus, this resulted in 3.89. The results have the

following indicators- Size of letters is appropriate for the target users (3.83); Font styles used are appropriate for the target user and easy to read (3.90); Spaces between letters and words facilitate reading (3.93). This means that the developed supplementary reading comprehension material is highly acceptable in terms of Typographical Organization.

Table 6: Acceptability of the Developed Supplementary Reading Comprehension Materials in Terms of Typographical Organization

Indicators	Average		
	Wx	Int	Rank
1. Size of letters is appropriate for the target users	3.83	HA	3
2. Font styles used are appropriate for the target user and easy to read	3.90	HA	2
3. Spaces between letters and words facilitate reading	3.93	HA	1
Average	3.89	HA	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Highly Acceptable (HA) 2.51 – 3.25 Acceptable (V) 1.00 - 1.75 Highly Rejected (HR) 1.76 - 2.50 Rejected (R)

Table 7 shows the results of the acceptability of the developed supplementary reading comprehension material in English integrating the local content of Tinambac, Camarines Sur for brigada pagbasa students which resulted in 3.87 interpreted as Highly Acceptable. Typographical Organization got the highest rank which resulted in 3.89 interpreted as Highly Acceptable. It was followed by

Language/Content/Format which resulted in 3.88 interpreted as Highly Acceptable. The third in rank was the Coherence and Clarity of Thought which resulted in 3.87 interpreted as Highly Acceptable. Book Lay-out and Design got the lowest rank which resulted in 3.84 interpreted as Highly Acceptable also.

Table 7: Acceptability of the Developed Supplementary Reading Comprehension Materials

Indicators	Wx	Int	Rank
1. Coherence and Clarity of Thought	3.87	HA	2.5
2. Language/Content/Format	3.88	HA	1
3. Book Lay-out and Design	3.84	HA	4
4. Typographical Organization	3.89	HA	2.5
AVERAGE	3.87	HA	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Highly Acceptable (HA)
2.51 – 3.25 Acceptable (V)
1.00 - 1.75 Highly Rejected (HR)
1.76 - 2.50 Rejected (R)

The level of the reading comprehension of the brigada pagbasa students using the developed supplementary reading material. An evaluation is given to the learners after the accomplishment of the developed supplementary reading comprehension material in English. Table 8 presents the test results of Grade 7 brigada pagbasa students after they were exposed to the developed supplementary reading comprehension material in English. Based on the data, in

literal, the indicator falls under Very Satisfactory (VS) where 5.048 is the mean with an 84.13 Performance Level; Inferential falls under Satisfactory (S) with a mean of 6.749 and a Performance Level of 74.99; and Critical falls under Satisfactory with mean 3.957 and 79.14 Performance Level. Additionally, based on the result, the over-all results implied that the over-all mean was 5.251 with a performance level of 79.42 which falls under Satisfactory.

Table 8: Level of the Reading Comprehension of the Brigada Pagbasa Students using the Developed Supplementary Reading Material

Reading Comprehension Level	No. of Items	Mean	SD	PL	Int	Rank
1. Literal	6	5.048	0.95	84.13	VS	1
2. Inferential	9	6.749	1.05	74.99	S	3
3. Critical	5	3.957	0.74	79.14	S	2
Average	20	5.251	0.913	79.42	S	

Legend: Performance Level (PL)

90 and above -	Outstanding (O)	SD - Standard Deviation
80-89 -	Very Satisfactory (VS)	Int - Interpretation
74-79 -	Satisfactory (S)	PL - Performance Level
66-73 -	Nearing Mastery (NM)	
65 below -	Needs Improvement (NI)	

D. The Significant Contribution of the Developed Supplementary Reading Material to the Reading Comprehension Skills of the Brigada Pagbasa Students

To test the improvement in the learners' test scores after they were exposed to the supplementary reading comprehension material in English integrating the local content of Tinambac, Camarines Sur, for brigada pagbasa recipients, the following data were gathered: As shown in the results, it can be noted that the regression equation is significant. The independent variable (brigada pagbasa material) significantly contributed to the level of reading

comprehension. The positive coefficient implies that an increase in the result of the supplementary reading material will result in a higher level of reading comprehension. Additionally, based on the result, it can be noted that there was a positive effect of the independent variable (brigada pagbasa material) on the dependent variable (developed supplementary reading material scores). Thus, the developed supplementary reading material could be concluded to be effective in enhancing and improving students reading comprehension skills.

Table 9: The Significant Contribution of the Developed Supplementary Reading Material to the Reding Comprehension Skills of the Brigada Pagbasa Students

Regression Analysis: Score versus brigada pagbasa material					
The regression equation is					
Score = 8.56 + 1.22 brigada pagbasa material					
Predictor	Coef	SE Coef	T	P	
Constant	8.5568	0.3315	25.81	0.000	
brigada pagbasa material	1.22283	0.04764	25.67	0.000	
S = 2.59057 R-Sq = 57.3% R-Sq(adj) = 57.2%					
Analysis of Variance					
Source	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Regression	1	4421.9	4421.9	658.90	0.000
Residual Error	491	3295.1	6.7		
Total	492	7717.0			

IV. DISCUSSION

Through the development of the supplementary reading comprehension material in English, the study further aimed to utilize the results of this study in crafting a policy recommendation that may be presented in the district of Tinambac. This study developed supplementary reading material to address the challenges in reading specifically the student’s reading comprehension level. The introduction of modular distance learning has made reading an even more difficult task to do. This led to the creation of supplemental reading materials with local content that incorporate location-specific content into language learning materials to encourage learners to value the subject matter as they study. Also, it is commended that teachers utilize the developed supplementary reading comprehension material in English integrating the local content of Tinambac in conducting the brigada pagbasa sessions, and might be a good solution to addressing the great lapses in reading among students. Therefore, this tool may be the innovation change to that current state.

The study revealed that the acceptability of the material posted an overall mean of 3. 87. This means that the local content-based reading material met the standards of a well-

planned learning material that resulted in a well-structured learning content that integrated literary text based on the local content of Tinambac. In addition, this means that the developed material achieved specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in a specified use. Positive feedback from the users is a good indicator that leads to the overall success of the creation.

As shown in the results, it can be noted that the regression equation is significant. The independent variable (brigada pagbasa material) significantly contributed to the level of reading comprehension. The positive coefficient implies that an increase in the result of the supplementary reading material will result in a higher level of reading comprehension. Additionally, based on the result, it can be noted that there was a positive effect of the independent variable (brigada pagbasa material) on the dependent variable (developed supplementary reading material scores). The developed supplementary reading comprehension material contributed significantly to the reading comprehension skills of the brigada pagbasa students based on the result of the regression analysis. A replication of this study is highly recommended to validate the findings of this study and to further reveal whether different study parameters or datagathering tools lead to the same results.

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